

Table S3. MS-validated ncORFs that introduce ambiguity into the interpretation of loss-of-function studies

NcORF	Locus name	Reference	Ambiguity type and description
NcORF1	<i>MtVPT2</i>	Liu et al., 2023c	Type 3. Both the refORF and the ncORF are affected in one line but only the refORF is affected in an additional line. Regardless of the phenotypic difference between the two lines, the true LOF phenotype of the ncORF should be assessed independently of the refORF.
NcORF2	<i>MtREV1</i>	Zhou et al., 2019	Type 5. Only the refORF is affected. The LOF phenotype can be attributed exclusively to the refORF. The ncORF should be disrupted independently of the refORF in a dedicated study.
NcORF4	<i>MtCKX6</i>	Wang et al., 2021a	Type 5. Only the refORF is affected. The LOF phenotype can be attributed exclusively to the refORF. The ncORF should be disrupted independently of the refORF in a dedicated study.
NcORF5	<i>MtWD40-1</i>	Pang et al., 2009; Meng et al., 2019b, 2023	Type 5. Only the refORF is affected. The LOF phenotype can be attributed exclusively to the refORF. The ncORF should be disrupted independently of the refORF in a dedicated study.
NcORF6	<i>MtTPST</i>	Zhang et al., 2025	Type 6. Only the ncORF is affected. The LOF phenotype can be attributed exclusively to the ncORF. The refORF should be disrupted independently of the ncORF in a dedicated study.
NcORF7	<i>MtAHL1</i>	Zhang et al., 2023a	Type 3. Both the refORF and the ncORF are affected in one line but only the refORF is affected in an additional line. Regardless of the phenotypic difference between the two lines, the true LOF phenotype of the ncORF should be assessed independently of the refORF.
NcORF8	<i>MtCAS31</i>	Li et al., 2018	Type 3. Both the refORF and the ncORF are affected in one line but only the refORF is affected in an additional line. Regardless of the phenotypic difference between the two lines, the true LOF phenotype of the ncORF should be assessed independently of the refORF.
NcORF10	<i>MtSCR</i>	Dong et al., 2021	Type 5. Only the refORF is affected. The LOF phenotype can be attributed exclusively to the refORF. The ncORF should be disrupted independently of the refORF in a dedicated study.
NcORF12	<i>MthGSHSb</i>	Frendo et al., 2001, 2005	Type 2. Both the refORF and the ncORF are affected (no additional mutant alleles are available). The LOF phenotype cannot be assigned to either of them without a dedicated study that mutagenizes the refORF and the ncORF independently.
NcORF13	<i>MtMYC2</i>	Guo et al., 2024	Type 3. Both the refORF and the ncORF are affected in one line but only the refORF is affected in an additional line. Regardless of the phenotypic difference between the two lines, the true LOF phenotype of the ncORF should be assessed independently of the refORF.

“LOF” stands for “loss-of-function”.